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Abbreviations list

API	Application Programming Interface
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DMP	Data Management Plan
DMP-IF	Data Management Plan-Interoperability Framework
DCAT	Data Catalogue Vocabulary
EOSC	European Open Science cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
IF	Interoperability Framework
IF/RA	Interoperability Framework/Reference Architecture
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation-Linked Data
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PDF	Portable Document Format
PID	Persistent Identifier
RA	Reference Architecture
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SKG	Scientific Knowledge Graph
SKG-IF	Scientific Knowledge Graph-Interoperability Framework

FAIR Assessment Tools Affected

CESSDA Metadata Validator (CMV)	https://cmv.cessda.eu/#!validation
CLARIN Curation Dashboard	https://curation.clarin.eu/
FAIR-Aware	https://fairaware.dans.knaw.nl/
FAIR Champion	https://tools.ostrails.eu/champion
FAIR Research Objects Assessment (FAIROS)	https://w3id.org/FAIROS/
FAIR Validator	https://catalogue.openaire.eu/service/openaire.metadata.validator/overview
FOOPS!	https://w3id.org/foops/
IVOA services Validation	https://wiki.ivoa.net/twiki/bin/view/IVOA/lvoaValidatorsSummary
PADC Validator	https://voparis-validation-reports.obspm.fr/validators/home

Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the second iteration of the **OSTrails FAIR Reference Model**. Like the first iteration (contained in [D1.2](#)), the objective is twofold:

- 1) Define the expectations of FAIRness in a flexible manner for a wide range of Digital Object types. In v1 we explored the feasibility and utility of creating a generic, flexible definition of a minimal level of FAIRness that could be applied to all Digital Objects, meeting the expectations of stakeholders and their data exploration agents (the result of this feasibility study is reiterated in [Section 2](#) below).
- 2) Define the reference model for how FAIRness measurements are expressed – both at the metadata and data levels, for consumption by users or automated agents. This is achieved by describing a novel schema for expressing the FAIRness assessment output and associated metadata from individual FAIR Tests, as well as from “Benchmarks”, i.e. sets of tests that represent higher-order expectations for FAIRness within a given community, or for a specific type of Digital Object.

This document provides an updated definition of the components and relations required for a complete FAIRness Reference Model and its implementation. It is closely linked to OSTrails deliverable [D1.4 – OSTrails Interoperability Reference Architecture V1](#), which provides the context within which this FAIRness Reference Model is being implemented.

Like the first iteration, v2 is guided by prior work arising from the FAIRCORE4EOSC Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT) [2]¹, as well as from concepts in the W3C Data Quality Vocabulary [3] and W3C Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT) [1]. The FAIRness Reference Model has been further informed by in-person “Hackathons” and attempts to align new pre-existing tools with the Reference Model. **At the time of writing, there are five FAIR Assessment tools that stand as exemplar reference implementations of the Model**, providing strong evidence that it is widely applicable, clearly defined, and easily implemented using a variety of tools and coding languages.

The present deliverable attempts to be a standalone document. As such, there is significant duplication with the prior iteration. The duplicative sections are to make this document internally complete. Where necessary, we explain the modest changes between v1 and v2, and their purpose. Most of the novelty in v2 comes from its extensions, particularly with respect to 1) a more elaborate definition of Benchmarks,

¹ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/compliance-assessment-toolkit-cat>

their associated Scoring Algorithms and their corresponding metadata, and 2) the addition of a new output model in the Guidance Element.

This document is organised as follows: [Section 1](#) briefly notes the methodological steps taken, which have not changed since v1. [Section 2](#) presents the conceptual model for FAIRness assessments, circumscribing the distinct components that are required to describe the full spectrum of expectations – from computational agents to the humans who must select the benchmarks and interpret the outputs. [Section 3](#) introduces the new Guidance Element and its emergent formal model. [Section 4](#) gives examples of how the components of the Reference Model may be used in different circumstances. [Section 5](#) presents the current state of up-take of the Reference Model among FAIR assessment and assistance tools, and examples of how the OSTrails Pilots are already using the model to create their domain-specific assessments. [Section 6](#) makes closing observations.

1. Methodology

This section is largely a summary of the equivalent section in [Deliverable 1.2](#), since the overall approach has not changed. Participants in the design of the FAIR Reference Model – primarily those who were authors of FAIR assessment tools² – undertook an informal survey of the behaviours of current FAIRness assessment platforms to catalogue the full range of expectations, data facets, and accompanying metadata that these tools were generating or manipulating. This included platforms both within and outside of OSTrails. A collaborative document encouraged participants to identify the similarities among their different approaches to FAIR assessment. The common elements found were grouped in “clusters”, which were then mapped to the concepts defined in the Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT) in collaboration with participants from the FAIRCORE4EOSC project [2]. The concepts in the CAT (e.g. “Metric”, “Benchmark” or “Test Output”) were chosen as the names of the clusters, which is reflected in how the conceptual components are named in the Reference Model.

It became quickly apparent that the different platforms instantiated different subsets of these elements and, moreover, that different Assessment Platforms that instantiated the same element might not expose it for external use or manipulation. The Reference Model solves this problem by avoiding reflecting the actual behaviour of any individual Platform; rather, the Model captures all concepts within the FAIR Assessment space, and the relationships between them, without considering whether any given Assessment Platform implements or exposes it or not. The granularity of the Reference Model does, however, allow it to be used to describe the overall behaviour of *any* FAIR assessment tool by, for example, imputation of functionality that can be presumed to exist in a tool, even if it is not exposed.

We then referred to existing standards such as W3C DCAT [1], W3C DQV [3], the EU DCAT Application Profile [4],³ and OpenAPI,⁴ to create generic metadata models for the instantiation of each component.

² <https://ostrails.eu/tools-overview>

³ <https://semiceu.github.io/DCAT-AP/releases/3.0.1/>

⁴ <https://swagger.io/specification/>

2. FAIR Reference Model Conceptual Components

As noted in [Deliverable 1.2](#) [5], the domain-, Digital Object-, and stakeholder-specific expectations for FAIRness do not easily lend themselves to an approach where a “minimal level of FAIRness” can be defined in a generic manner, for all Digital Objects, for all communities, or for all purposes. Rather, those expectations suggest that FAIRness expectations must be flexible, dynamic, reusable, and most importantly, *transparent and FAIR*. This context informed the decisions made about how to design the FAIR Reference Model and its components.

[Section 2.1](#) defines the core components that make up the FAIR Reference Model, and how these have evolved from v1 to v2 of that model.

[Section 2.2](#) defines the output of a test or a set of tests (such as those arising from execution of a Benchmark), and the minor changes that have occurred in the output model between v1 and v2 of the Reference Model.

[Section 2.3](#) introduces the main enhancements of the Reference Model, focusing on the extension of the core model to represent Benchmark Scoring Algorithm outputs.

The new Guidance Element model is sufficiently novel to deserve to be addressed separately in [Section 3](#).

Reference Model: Definition

A Reference Model is a conceptual framework used to describe, understand, or guide the development of an area of interest, system, or process.

- Reference models are often abstract rather than specific, providing a high-level overview that can be applied across different scenarios or adapted to specific needs. They serve as a blueprint or template.
- They typically define the key components of a system, service, or process, along with the relationships between these components. This might include layers, stages, or modules.
- Reference models are used to establish standards or common practices. They help in ensuring interoperability, consistency, and understanding across different implementations by different entities.
- They guide the design, development, or analysis of systems or strategies by offering a common vocabulary and conceptual structure. They're particularly useful for complex systems where understanding the big picture is crucial before diving into details.

2.1. FAIR Reference Model Components

The core set of Reference Model components were identified with the guidance of the FAIRCORE4EOSC Compliance Assessment Toolkit [2]. The components are split in three categories depending on whether they are related to the **Conceptual** (structured or unstructured narrative), **Software**, and **Data level**. **Figure 1** shows the main relationships between these components, relating all categories to each other. In addition, there is a higher level of Conceptual object we call a **Dimension**, which we adapt from W3C DQV to represent an established FAIR principle (e.g. FAIR Principle F1) that motivates the need for the creation of a FAIR test (or set of tests).

The most significant changes in the core component model between v1 and v2 relate to the naming of the components and relations. We became aware that our nomenclature was not aligned with the way our target communities perceived these concepts. An example of such misalignment was around the concept of a “Benchmark”, where our users frequently considered a Benchmark to be a “score” (i.e. an assessment output) while we regarded it as a list of metrics and their expected outcomes.

The three Conceptual-level components involved in the FAIR Reference Model are:

- **Dimension** "High-level, often pre-existing conceptual objective criteria considered relevant to assess the quality of Digital Objects (cf. W3C Data Quality Vocabulary, dqv:Dimension). Dimensions should be chosen to be subject- and implementation-agnostic; but they may be refined differently to suit the needs of individual communities. The FAIR principles⁵ [6] are an example of such criteria. Dimensions are distinct from the other conceptual components in that in OSTrails we do not attempt to define the structure/representation of a Dimension."
- **Benchmark**: a narrative definition of how to interpret the Test Result Set resulting from the application of one or more Metrics to a Digital Object. A Benchmark is also a community-specific grouping of metrics whose narrative describes how a community defines FAIR. Communities can choose the granularity of their benchmarks with regards to subject area and Digital Object type. This means that benchmarks may be agnostic of object type or subject area, or may be scoped as tightly as required by the benchmark authors.
- **Metric**: Narrative description that a Test must wholly implement. Each metric should implement exactly one dimension (e.g. one sub-principle from the FAIR Principles). Metrics may be domain-agnostic or not.

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.WWI10U>

The two Software level components in the FAIR Reference Model are:

- **Test:** A software object or defined manual workflow that examines some aspect of a Digital Object, and outputs a Test Result (i.e. pass/fail/indeterminate). Each Test is an instantiation of one Metric, executed to assess a Digital Object according to the relevant Metric.
- **Scoring Algorithm:** A piece of code or manual workflow that implements a Benchmark, and outputs a Benchmark score. Algorithms are executed to create community-specific value judgements on the outcomes of tests. They specify the exact set of tests which are to be run by the assessment service together with weightings for each of these tests. Algorithms contextualise the sum of all test results for a Benchmark into a final quantitative result for the assessment.

All these components (excluding Dimensions) have metadata descriptors following a formal model (see FAIR Reference Model Component Descriptors).

The two data-level components are:

- **Test Result:** The output from a test. As outlined in V1 of the Reference Model, we require that tests are very precise, and can have only “pass”, “fail”, or “indeterminate” as possible outcomes. The output will include metadata (e.g. a progress log) that can be used to interpret the provenance behind the output. Aggregations of Test Results, referred to as “**Test Result Sets**”, also have a defined structure.
- **Benchmark Score:** The output from a Scoring Algorithm, representing the measurement of some Benchmark as a numeric or controlled vocabulary score and the post-assessment guidance.

Table 1 shows the modification in nomenclature between v1 and v2, and further shows that the core model, as described in [Deliverable 1.2](#), is preserved in v2. **Figure 1** shows the component/relationship diagram for Reference Model v2.

Table 1. Mapping entity/relation changes between v1 and v2 of the Reference Model.

COMPONENT/RELATION NAME V1	COMPONENT/RELATION NAME V2	PURPOSE
Algorithm	[Benchmark] Scoring Algorithm	The class of entities representing code-level artefacts that execute one or more FAIR tests on a target digital object to obtain a score.

Assessment Outcome	Benchmark Score	The output from a Scoring Algorithm
prov:wasDerivedFrom	ftr:outputFromAlgorithm	Relation between BenchmarkScore and ScoringAlgorithm
-	ftr:TestResultSet	The aggregated output of all tests executed by a ScoringAlgorithm
-	ftr:scoredTestResults	Relation between a BenchmarkScore and the individual TestResultSet that was used to derive the Benchmark Score.
-	prov:hadMember	The relation between a TestResultSet and the individual TestResults that comprise it.

Figure 1. Components of the FAIR Reference Model and the relations between them.

These definitions are actively used by the participating Pilots⁶ to define community-specific expectations for FAIRness, as well as to execute assessment of those expectations.

2.2. Output Structures and v1/v2 Changes

We have created a Linked Data model defined within the FAIR Testing Resource Vocabulary⁷ to represent the output from a Test and the aggregation of multiple test outputs, and a model for capturing provenance information about that invocation, based on W3C PROV-O [7]. These have been formalised and published as the FAIR Testing Resource Vocabulary (<https://w3id.org/ftr#>). The current model is depicted in **Figure 2**. Instantiation of these models is achieved using (preferentially) JSON-LD formatted data,

⁶ <https://ostrails.eu/case-studies>

⁷ <https://w3id.org/ftr>

to manually apply these schemas, a validation tool is being developed¹¹ to support the compliance of different FTR-based applications. This tool will allow uploading an FTR-compliant document and provide an easy-to-read report of any detected errors.

2.3. Extensions of the v1 Reference Model

Figure 2 shows an entity-relationship diagram with the end-to-end latest FTR specification. The main changes include the addition of the Benchmark Score class, and the Guidance Context class.

The Benchmark Score class is an entity designed to store the results of executing a Scoring Algorithm over a set of test results. In summary, the Benchmark Score includes a value with the final assessment described by the algorithm (which can be a numerical value such as 90% or a qualitative assessment, such as “benchmark from organization X has been achieved”), together with provenance information: an explanation (a log) detailing how the score was calculated, the algorithm used and the set of test results obtained.

The Guidance Context class is used by test results to describe actionable guidance steps for users when a test fails, together with a link to the corresponding Guidance Element that motivates it (see [Section 3](#)). Guidance Elements may include specifications, good practices or tutorials developed by the community to help achieve a given principle.

2.4. Reference Model REST API

To ease compliance with the operations defined in the FAIR Reference Model components, we defined a REST API specification by using the OpenAPI standard. There are two “types” of calls in the FAIR Reference Model: 1) Calls intended to retrieve information about components (e.g. tests, metrics, etc.) and calls intended to trigger the execution of an activity (such as a test or an algorithm). The latter kinds of calls are prefixed with the /assess/ endpoint. An OpenAPI template specification for the reference model is available online including examples and method calls.¹²

¹¹ <https://github.com/OSTrails/FAIR-assessment-record-validator>

¹²

https://github.com/OSTrails/FAIR_testing_resource_vocabulary/blob/main/development/api/open_api_description.yaml

2.4.1. GET calls

Each of following methods will return metadata of the artifact in JSON-LD, following the FTR specification. The method MUST accept a GET string with key/value as in **Table 2**.

Table 2. Specification of GET API calls.

METHOD	PARAMETER	EXPECTED RESULT
/tests/	testid	A list with all the test identifiers supported by the tool. When an id is sent, a DCAT record in JSON-LD is returned.
/benchmarks/	bmid	A list with all the benchmark identifiers supported by the tool. When an id is sent, a DCAT record in JSON-LD is returned.
/metrics/	mid	A list with all the metrics identifiers supported by the tool. When an id is sent, a DCAT record in JSON-LD is returned.
/algorithms/	aid	A list with all the algorithms identifiers supported by the tool. When an id is sent, a DCAT record in JSON-LD is returned.

2.4.2. POST calls

All post requests must submit a body with the resource to assess as shown in the snippet below. **Table 3** further specifies the API design for POST calls:

```
{
  "resource_identifier": "https://w3id.org/example#"
}
```

Table 3. Specification of POST API calls

METHOD	PARAMETER	EXPECTED RESULT
/assess/test/	testid	A list with all the test identifiers supported by the tool. When an id is sent, a DCAT record in JSON-LD is returned.
/assess/algorithm/	algoid	A list with all the benchmark identifiers supported by the tool. When an id is sent, a DCAT record in JSON-LD is returned.

In some cases, FAIR assessments may require inspecting multiple large resources. This is, for example, the case when assessing Research Objects.¹³ In such situations, the API may not immediately return the test results in JSON-LD format. Instead, it returns a JSON response with the following information:

```
{
  "ticket_id":          "<ID          of          the          response>"
}
```

In this case, the API returns an HTTP status code **202 (Accepted)**, indicating that the assessment request has been successfully created. Additionally, the response header **Location** contains a link where the results will be available once generated.

3. Guidance Elements

3.1. FAIR Guidance Reference Model: Creation and Structure

3.1.1. Introduction – Guidance in the FAIR Ecosystem

Guidance is a broad, multifaceted concept that encompasses many forms of advice and examples of best practices. Different communities have produced guidelines, recommendations, best practices, standards, FAQs, procedures/instructions, and more for the generation of research Digital Objects – all of which we refer to collectively as “guidance”. In OSTrails, guidance is paired with FAIR assessment results: each result may contain a pointer for users to help them interpret the assessment results or guide them to improve some aspect of their metadata.

A survey of the landscape of guidance provision with automated FAIR assessment tools and investigating other EOSC initiatives such as the FAIRCORE4EOSC Compliance Assessment Toolkit and FAIRsFAIR FAIR-Aware tool¹⁴ were undertaken, to ensure that the FAIR Guidance Reference Model (FGRM) does not duplicate effort and is maximally interoperable with other FAIR guidance initiatives. In our assessment of guidance associated with assessment tools it became clear that only a small number gave guidance that could be evaluated by a user to appraise the reusability of Digital Object in their research, or by a researcher wishing to improve the FAIRness of the Digital Object they

¹³ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

¹⁴ <https://fairaware.dans.knaw.nl>

are about to share. Many such tools provided only ‘debug’ information on the pass/fail status of tests, whereas only a few, such as FAIR EVA^{15,16}, FAIR Champion¹⁷ and FOOPS!¹⁸ [8] provide information on how to improve FAIRness. Moreover, guidance on improving and understanding FAIRness exists external to the assessment tools, sometimes in discipline-specific guidance websites¹⁹ or generic study tools such as FAIR-Aware. This fragmentation motivated OSTrails to standardise and formalise a guidance vocabulary, ensuring that guidance information can be classified, shared, and linked across FAIR assessment frameworks in a consistent way.

In the context of FAIR assessment, incorporating guidance can help both users seeking to improve the FAIRness of their Digital Objects and those reusing existing digital resources to understand why a criterion is important and what they can do to improve FAIRness. The FAIR-IMPACT All Hands Meeting (The Hague, Oct 2024)²⁰ highlighted the “vocabulary and definitions” workshop on guidance and called for a common understanding of guidance types and their relationships. In response, OSTrails set out to design a FAIR guidance model that can link guidance to assessment model elements (principles, criteria, metrics, tests etc.) in a technology-agnostic way. The result is a structured guidance model framework and an accompanying ontology to describe guidance elements in a machine-readable form expressed in RDF. This section describes how the model was created, its structure, and how it has been implemented for use by technical stakeholders.

3.1.2. Guidance Types and Focus Areas

A first step was to define a vocabulary of guidance types, capturing the different forms that guidance can take. **Table 4 summarises the main guidance types identified.**

¹⁵ <https://fair.csic.es/en>

¹⁶ FAIR EVA provides explanation on the FAIR indicator it is testing and how it is being tested. It provides technical feedback on what it has found or not. It also provides ‘tips’ with external links in the form of recommendations and or best practises to guide the user. It is repository specific and is part of the repository ingest workflow.

¹⁷ <https://tools.ostrails.eu/champion/>

¹⁸ https://foops.linkeddata.es/FAIR_validator.html

¹⁹ An example is the LTER-LIFE “A hands-on guide to FAIR and structured ecological data” <https://lter-life.github.io/FDFDT-Manual/> . LTER-LIFE is a research infrastructure aimed at developing digital twins of ecosystems.

²⁰ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/second-all-hands-meeting-hague-15-17-october-2024>

Table 4. Overview of main guidance types identified by the project.

GUIDANCE TYPE	DESCRIPTION
FAQ (Frequently Asked Questions)	A thematically organized collection of guidance in Q&A form. An FAQ provides answers or instructions for common queries, often aggregating multiple practices or mini guidelines under each question.
Procedure	A step-by-step method, protocol, or procedure to accomplish something with a high certainty of the expected outcome. These are “how-to” style guidance items (modelled as Procedure in the ontology).
Framework	A broad set of guiding principles for achieving an objective. (In the ontology, a Guideline is modelled as a Framework – a collection of related recommendations and best practices.)
Benchmark	A context-specific best practice linked to a particular FAIR criterion. (Often these appear as guidelines tied directly to a FAIR sub-principle or metric.)
Best Practice	Describes current accepted practices and the state-of-the-art. Best practices are established methods or techniques that have proven to effectively achieve desired outcomes in a specific context.
Standard	A formal specification or community-endorsed standard that serves as guidance. Standards represent a high level of consensus or requirement (e.g. an ISO standard or community standard to follow).

FAIR-Aware uses three interrogatives: “what?”, “why?” and “how?” plus “more information” to categorise guidance information for the user. These four classifiers form the basis of the instantiations of the Focus Area in the FAIR Guidance reference model. In other words, guidance can target different aspects of why, what, or how something should be done:

- **Motivation (Why)** – The reason or rationale behind the guidance. For example, explaining *why* a particular FAIR practice matters or what benefit it brings (addresses the “purpose” of the guidance). Answering 'Why follow this guideline?'
- **Meaning / Implementation (What)** – The substance of the guidance: *what* specific actions or requirements should be met. This focus covers the concrete things that need to be done or to be in place. Answering 'What does this mean?'

- **Process (How)** – The procedural aspect: *how* to implement the guidance in practice. This often corresponds to instructions, methods, or workflows to follow to achieve the desired outcome. Answering 'How should this be done?'
- **Additional Information (More)** – Provides additional useful information about the topic, such as context, examples, tools, or references. Answering 'What else is relevant or helpful to know?'

Every guidance element is tagged with one of these categories to clarify its intended role. For instance, a guidance might be labelled as “Motivation” if it explains why a principle is important, versus “Process” if it gives an actual protocol on how to comply. Tagging helps users filter guidance based on their needs (e.g. whether they are looking for conceptual justification or practical steps).

3.1.3. External Resource Types for Guidance

To consider that guidance content can reside in many forms and locations, the Reference Model introduces the notion of Resource Type to identify the source of the guidance. A Guidance Element may point to an external resource, such as a webpage, document (plain or formatted text, PDF), or video. The format of the Description and Title text properties of such a Guidance Element (such as plain text, Markdown or URL) is currently still under discussion and will be decided upon later within the remainder of the project. The following external resource types have been identified:

- **Direct External Reference:** The guidance is available as a web-accessible resource (e.g. an HTML page, PDF document, etc.) reachable via a URL. In such cases, the guidance element stores the link (and optionally a fragment identifier or query parameters) to refer to the relevant section. For example, a guidance element might point to a specific section of a community guideline webpage or an instructional video.
- **Persistent Identifier Reference:** Instead of a direct URL, a PID (such as a DOI or Handle) can be used, which resolves to the guidance resource. This redirection ensures long-term access if the content moves.
- **Annotation Reference:** The model can reference a precise fragment of a resource via annotations. For instance, one could annotate a specific paragraph in a PDF or highlight text in an HTML page that contains the guidance or use annotation frameworks.
- **Locally Stored Guidance:** In some cases, the guidance text or instructions might be stored directly in the automated assessment tool. The model can accommodate storing the guidance element’s content internally while still tagging it appropriately.

All guidance External Resources are characterised by their type (e.g. Web Page, PDF, API response, etc.) and how they're accessed (via URL, via API calls, or local storage). The goal is flexibility: guidance can live anywhere on the Web or locally, and the model must record how to retrieve it. This ensures that when a guidance element is presented to a user, the system knows whether to display an embedded snippet, link out to an external site, call an API, or show a local description. By supporting various resource types, the FAIR Guidance Reference Model can integrate guidance from diverse sources (e.g. a [Zenodo](#) PDF, a [GitHub](#) README, a knowledge base entry, etc.) in a unified way.

3.2. Model Structure and Schema

Each Guidance Element in the model is represented as a distinct item (with its own identifier) that is linked to a set of descriptive tags along the Dimensions described above. At a minimum, every Guidance Element is tagged with: (1) the related FAIR criterion (and implicitly the principle) to which it pertains, (2) a Guidance Type, (3) a Resource type indicating where/how the guidance content was obtained, and (4) a Focus Area (purpose). These define the essential character of the guidance. In addition, a Guidance Element must reference a Source, which means specifying the provenance from where it has come; for example, a FAIR assessment tool, research infrastructure, discipline, or author. A Guidance Element can also be linked to other elements of the FAIR Test Results Reference Model besides the primary criterion, or FAIR Principle. For example, a Guidance Element could be linked to a specific benchmark, metric or test that it helps address.

In **Figure 3**, the Guidance Element (scribed blue circle) is linked to a Focus Area (Motivation, Process, etc.) and has an “is of type” relationship to a specific guidance subtype (yellow and blue nodes such as *Standard*, *Procedure*, *Benchmark*, *Best Practice*, *FAQ*). The Guidance Element is also connected to a Reference/External Resource node, which can be manifested as a web page, PID, API, or annotation. The model also allows guidance elements to optionally refer to one another – e.g. a Recommendation might refer to one or more Standards.

Figure 3. Conceptual diagram of the current proposal for the FAIR Guidance model

3.3. Ontology Integration: FAIR Guidance Vocabulary (FGV)

To formalise the guidance model (**Figure 3**) for reuse and interoperability, the FAIR Guidance Vocabulary (FGV) was created. It is an OWL/RDFS ontology that captures the classes and relationships in the model. The FGV ontology (available via the namespace URI <https://w3id.org/fgv#>) provides a semantic schema for Guidance Elements described above, making each concept dereferenceable as Linked Open Data and thus enabling cross-system interoperability. The ontology was developed alongside the FAIR Testing Resource Vocabulary (FTR) and reuses where possible the same external classes from

other ontologies for (super)classes and relations. The ontology is chiefly focused on three main classes:

1. **GuidanceElement**: A discrete item of guidance (standard, procedure, FAQ, etc.) that can be categorized by one or more Guidance Dimensions such as Domain, Motivation, Actor, etc.
2. **ExternalResource**: A resource that represents or provides access to a piece of guidance. May be a Persistent Identifier, a Web Page, or an Annotation.
3. **FocusArea**: A conceptual aspect or interpretive dimension describing the emphasis of a guidance element — typically answering 'What?', 'How?', or 'Why?'.

In essence, each **GuidanceElement** in the model can be instantiated as one of the more specific types (Procedure, Standard, FAQ, etc.) which are also part of the FGV ontology. **Figure 4** shows the class diagram and their relation types. The central class **fgv:GuidanceElement** is linked to a **fgv:FocusArea** which answers What/How/Why. Guidance elements can be manifested, or refer to an **fgv:ExternalResource**, which can be an **fgv:WebPage**, **fgv:PersistentIdentifier**, **fgv:Annotation**, or **fgv:ObjectOrServiceAPI**. The diagram also shows subclasses of **GuidanceElement** for each guidance type. The yellow boxes indicate classes reused from other ontologies. Note that the FTR can be connected to the FGV – For instance, a pointer from a **ftr:Test** to **fgv:BestPractice**", which is a subclass of the **Guidance Element**.

The FGV ontology reuses several vocabularies to avoid duplication or reinventing terms. For example, it links guidance to FAIR principles through a property (e.g., **fgv:relatesToFAIRPrinciple**) that expects a SKOS Concept for the principle. It also classifies **fgv:GuidanceElement** as a subclass of **schema:CreativeWork**. The **ExternalResource** representation leverages **Semantics of Information Ontology (SIO)** for concepts like web resources, Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) etc., using properties like *resolvesTo* to connect a PID to the actual web page. Each class and property in FGV has a stable URI under the **w3id.org** namespace, meaning that any system can dereference that URI to get more information and support content negotiation. This **Linked Open Data** approach allows linking to related concepts in other ontologies. A clear opportunity for linkage is the **FAIR Testing Resource (FTR)** vocabulary (<https://w3id.org/ftr#>), which models FAIR assessment results and their relationship to tests and metrics. Because guidance elements are linked to metrics/tests in the CAT model, one could use semantic links between FGV and FTR: for example, connecting a **fgv:GuidanceElement** to an **ftr:TestResult** or **ftr:Metric** that it helps satisfy. This may enable rich queries, like “for each metric, retrieve associated guidance URIs”.

Figure 4. Class diagram of the FAIR Guidance Vocabulary (FGV), illustrating core classes and their relations.

At the OSTrails Hackathon event at UPM in 2025, the attendees unanimously agreed to begin formalising the FGV model and coding their outputs to prepare for it. There was also a general agreement that, while guidance could happen before, during, and after a FAIR assessment, the focus of our work in OSTrails would be post-assessment guidance, since that is where we require definitions for interoperability between guidance and assessment.

Two additional proposals adopted by the attendees will govern how this element is used in FAIR assessment outputs:

- 1) **Guidance should be made available at all “levels” of assessment** – test results and test result sets - the latter generally derived from the execution of a scoring algorithm, where the tests to be executed are either defined by, or circumscribed by, the associated community-specific benchmark. This means that guidance itself can have a wide range of granularity, from advice about solving low-level problems like HTTP message header violations, all the way to community-specific advice about which ontologies should be used to annotate a given digital object.
- 2) **The guidance provided in the output from the testing tool is entirely at the discretion of the author of that tool.** This is important because it releases the author from any responsibility to update the guidance they provide as external resources are updated, or as new guidance resources become available. Test/algorithm authors may update the guidance they provide as they see fit, but this will is generally not expected from them. Importantly, however, *this does not*

preclude (nor discourage) any third-party from post-processing the logs provided by a given test or algorithm and adding new or updated Guidance Elements to the output (in fact, this could easily become a “cottage industry”, where communities might create entire guidance suites related to, for example, training in best practices for their community). This is a key reason to explain why the guidance element is clearly separated from the core FTR model via the FTR Guidance “Context” node: post-processors can easily add new guidance to that context node without affecting the structure or content of the assessment output itself, leaving it untouched for use and interpretation by other FAIR assessment tools.

[Section 4.2.2](#) describes how Guidance Elements are catalogued, searched, and used (pending transformation into FAIR formats).

4. Exemplar use of the Reference Model

The FAIR Reference Model (RM) is composed of a set of conceptual entity-relations, and a schema for instantiating those entities in a manner that can be stored, discovered, and reused. The RM does not recommend any specific architecture for how these discovery and reuse processes should be implemented and is agnostic to those decisions. Here, we present one example of how instances of the RM may be used in a production setting.

4.1. Metadata Registries to store RM instances – generic view

While instances of the RM are in principle just documents on the Web that could be indexed by any search engine, in practice it makes more sense to submit these objects to an appropriate Registry to facilitate later discovery and reuse. Registries “harvest” the Web metadata record either by autonomously discovering it on the Web, or via some submission process. **Figure 5** shows the four core types of instances defined by the RM, and a generic process of extracting and storing that information for later discovery via query. The APIs for the registries and search functions are outside of the scope of the FAIR RM, and the OSTrails Assessment IF generally.

Figure 5. A generic architecture for how FAIR RM instances could be stored and discovered for the purpose of designing FAIR Assessment tools.

4.2. Metadata Registries Selected for the OSTrails Reference Implementation

4.2.1. FAIRassist/FAIRsharing and the OSTrails FDP Index

To fulfil the OSTrails Pilot Use Cases, it was necessary to implement the RM and choose its accessory dependencies, such as registries. In the current implementation of the OSTrails FAIR Assessment Interoperability Framework (or Assess-IF for short), we have selected registries created and maintained independently that participate in OSTrails. These fall into two categories – those that store instances of conceptual components such as dimensions/principles, metrics and benchmarks (the green components in **Figure 5**), and those that store instances of software-level objects (the blue components in **Figure 5**). In the current implementation of OSTrails Assess-IF components, storage and discovery of instances of conceptual level entities is achieved by the FAIRassist registry (<https://fairassist.org/registry>) powered by FAIRsharing (<https://fairsharing.org/>), while storage and discovery of code level entities is achieved by the FAIR Data Point Index. The cross-linking between these registries enables the Assess-IF by connecting software components, conceptual components and the FAIRsharing graph of standards, databases and policies, including:

- A benchmark groups metrics, each of which point to specific principles/dimensions, all registered in FAIRassist,
- Metrics store information on the FAIR tools that are aware of them and the tests registered in FDP that implement them
- Tests in FDP are described in a scoring algorithm,
- Scoring algorithms link to benchmarks
- The Digital Object types (e.g. datasets, terminologies) applicable to the metric or benchmark,

- The expert community or domain appropriate to all components within FDP and FAIRassist,
- The standards or policies that are involved in the FAIR evaluation, and
- The assessment tools or platforms that run the evaluations.

Figure 6. The two metadata registries used in the current implementation of the OSTrails FAIR-IF to store and discover FAIR Reference Model instances. This is a specific implementation of the generalised architecture shown in Figure 4.

To the greatest extent possible, we will be harmonising the API that allows the search of these two registry types. The conceptual level registry (FAIRsharing) is used for both Benchmark and Metric authoring activities as shown in Figure 5. Both types of registries are used in the process diagram in Figure 6.

4.2.2. Guidance Dashboard

The FAIR Guidance Reference Model can be implemented directly by any FAIR evaluation provider. It has been implemented in a prototype Guidance Dashboard – a web application that allows users to browse, drill down and filter the Guidance Elements (pending their transformation into machine-readable syntaxes) in the guidance knowledge base (<https://fairassessment.dansdemo.nl/guidance>). A screenshot is provided in Figure 7. Users can drill down by various facets: for example, one can filter guidance by *Guidance Type* (to see only “Recommendations” vs “Standards” etc.), or by *Focus Area* (to show only “how-to” procedural guidance vs motivational context). The

interface also supports filtering by FAIR principle or criterion, so an assessor focusing on a particular principle (say F1 or R1) can view all guidance items related to that principle. The goal of the dashboard is to make it easy to find the most relevant guidance for a given scenario. Users can combine filters (e.g. “Show me all Best Practices for principle R1 that have *Why* focus”) such that the system will then display a list of guidance entries matching those tags, each with a short description and a link or expandable section to view the full content. A tool will be able to link to the Guidance Element in the knowledge base by providing a deep link to the Dashboard UI or the underlying (REST) API response.

Figure 7. Guidance dashboard with example test data. The left pane facilitates searching and filtering. The right pane displays the matching guidance elements.

On the back end, the Dashboard is powered by a knowledge base (the extended CAT Model Database where guidance elements and tags are stored) and an Elasticsearch²¹ index for fast querying. The data from the PostgreSQL²² based knowledge base is indexed into Elasticsearch to enable quick text searches and facet aggregations. This architecture allows the Dashboard to support free-text search across guidance content, as well as instantaneous filtering counts on the facets.

This website also provides a RESTful API for extracting Guidance Elements. The Guidance API (and documentation, see **Figure 8**) exposes endpoints to retrieve guidance information in JSON format for machine-to-machine access. It offers operations to list available controlled vocabulary entries (dimensions) and to query guidance elements with various filters. For example, a client can GET /v1/registry/guidancetype to fetch the

²¹ <https://www.elastic.co/elasticsearch>

²² <https://www.postgresql.org/>

list of all guidance types or GET /v1/registry/focus for the focus area list. More importantly, one can query /v1/registry/guidance_elements/ with query parameters (or a JSON payload) specifying any combination of tags to filter by, essentially replicating what the dashboard UI does, but via API. There are also endpoints to retrieve a specific guidance element by its identifier, and to register new guidance elements or update them (with authentication).

Figure 8. Screenshot of the FAIR Guidance API documentation (Swagger UI), showing available endpoints for retrieving guidance dimensions and elements.

Using this API, a third-party application (for instance, a FAIR evaluation service or a repository platform) can programmatically fetch guidance relevant to a particular assessment result. For example, after running an automated FAIR evaluation, a tool could

call the Guidance API to get links to guidance items for each criterion where the object fell short or needs improvement. The API returns structured data (JSON), which includes details on the Guidance Element details, its tags, and links to any external resources. This machine-readable output means guidance can be delivered beyond the web dashboard, e.g. it can be integrated into a tool. Finally, the Guidance API includes some administrative operations such as exporting the entire guidance registry or syncing it to the Elasticsearch index. The system is built with maintainability in mind, ensuring that as the guidance knowledge base grows, it can be easily kept in synchronisation.

4.3. The role of Reference Model and Standards Repositories in Authoring

Unlike the SKG and DMP Interoperability Frameworks, the architecture of the Assess-IF was largely pre-determined before the launch of OSTrails, with approximately 30 FAIR Assessment tools already in existence at the time of launch (as discussed in Deliverable [D1.4 - OSTrails Interoperability Reference Architecture V1](#)). However, once the FAIR Reference Model was defined, and we had migrated the existing Metrics and Benchmarks from the FAIR Champion and FOOPS! platforms into this model, we engaged with the Pilots to begin cataloguing their community-specific expectations. This exercise is in an early phase at the time of writing, with early discussions taking place in a “sandbox^[OBJ]”²³ Column “J” in the spreadsheet captures the details of the community expectations, while rows 11 to 23 capture needs for specific pilot tests. For example:²⁴ Column “J” in the spreadsheet captures the details of the community expectations, while rows 11 to 23 capture needs for specific pilot tests. For example:

²⁴

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1Oh_4yldeK62_xLdDrN31lzTp7pJnAmZk8MaxSsvSbZy/e dit?gid=179152345#gid=179152345

Listing 1. Example of a community-specific Benchmark from PANOSC

input: DataCite DOI (could be dataset, publication ...)

output:

- if the DOI is not hosted by DataCite returns "fail DOI not found in DataCite"

- if the DOI has "scheme" field associated to PaNET ontology returns "success the Datacite DOI links to a PaNET technique" else returns "fail". The metadata of the DOI contains a reference to a Photon and Neutron Experimental Technique (PANET) (source DataCite API subjects). Please edit the DOI metadata if possible.

Success example: 10.5442/ND000001 => <https://api.datacite.org/doi/10.5442/ND000001>

This spreadsheet is expected to be useful for those highly knowledgeable of both FAIR and the technical requirements for associated tests, but it can present a challenge for some participants. Therefore, additional engagement with all Pilots is occurring in an iterative fashion via workshops and one-to-one Q&A sessions using a narrative template document [9]. This document helps Pilots capture benchmark and metric requirements by using textual narratives and includes documentation and instructions aimed at those new to the creation of FAIR definitions. Generic metrics are provided for almost all FAIR principles, and Pilots are encouraged to review and re-use these wherever possible. Iterative refinement of these documents will allow Pilots to progress from human-readable definitions of FAIR to production and implementation of all components as active FAIR benchmarks.

In both the spreadsheet and document methods, the individual conditions detailed in the proposed community Benchmark will often be implemented as individual FAIR Metrics and their associated tests. The Benchmark will then be authored that aggregates those Metrics and describes the conditions under which the outputs will be considered a "success".

These instances of the Reference Model concepts will need to be registered for discovery and reuse by all tools implementing the Assess-IF. Support for **authoring and registration** of Tests, Metrics, and Benchmarks therefore requires appropriate registries. For example, when authoring a community-specific Benchmark emerging from engagement with a Pilot, users would select the Dimension of FAIRness they are attempting to test (e.g. the presence of a license in the metadata of the Digital Object), and then search for license-associated FAIR Metrics in a registry where the record of the Metric would indicate which community(ies) encourage the use of that Metric. This would progress iteratively until a Benchmark covering all FAIR Dimensions of interest has been completed. This Benchmark would then also be registered in the Standards registry for

discovery and reuse by others in their community. This kind of interaction is depicted in the sequence diagram in .

Figure 9. A sequence diagram showing the series of steps involving metadata and/or standards registries when authoring a Benchmark in the OSTRails Assessment IF

By using FAIRsharing (<https://fairsharing.org>) as the standards registry describing the Metrics and Benchmarks, OSTRails enables discoverability and fosters reuse, laying groundwork for the complex issue of governance, and will be tackled at a later stage in the project. In FAIRsharing, the records of Metrics and related Benchmarks will be cross-linked to the records of the FAIR Principles they implement, to help with navigation and findability. Furthermore, Metrics assessing use of Standards will also be cross-linked to relevant standard records, such as identifier schemas (https://fairsharing.org/search?recordType=identifier_schema), reporting requirements (https://fairsharing.org/search?recordType=reporting_guideline), terminologies (https://fairsharing.org/search?recordType=terminology_artefact), model and formats (https://fairsharing.org/search?recordType=model_and_format).

A FAIR assessment authoring tool has been developed²⁵ to aid communities select and configure their own benchmarks, metrics, tests and scoring algorithms according to the FTR application profile requirements. The authoring tool guides users through a series of steps with a questionnaire, produces an FTR compliant description, and submits the assessment components to the corresponding metadata registries, such as FAIRsharing or the OSTRails FDP Index.

²⁵ <https://ostrails-fair.fair-wizard.com/wizard/>

4.4. The role of Reference Model and Standards Repositories in Testing

Running a FAIR assessment requires a variety of data, metadata, and standards and repositories that hold relevant Digital Objects (DO). An exemplar (though not exclusive) interaction with various facets of the FAIR Reference Model is shown in **Figure 10**. Users run a FAIR Assessment Tool, providing the PID of the DO of interest, and information about the community to which they belong. The Assessment Tool executes a lookup on a FAIR Benchmark Registry (FAIRsharing in the OSTrails Assessment IF), which returns metadata about that Benchmark, including the aggregated FAIR Metrics. The Assessment Tool then executes a lookup on another registry that contains definitions of FAIR Test (called the “FAIR Test Index Fair Data Point” (FDP) in the Reference Model), which returns the OpenAPI interface URLs for tests corresponding to each Metric. The Assessment Tool then engages each FAIR Test iteratively using the PID of the DO. The FAIR Test engages the Data Repository to which the DO belongs to gather data/metadata. When necessary, it will also engage with an external Standards Registry (FAIRsharing in the OSTrails Assessment IF) to retrieve further information, e.g. about the metadata schema required by a particular community, to improve the accuracy of the assessment. Additionally, the FAIR Test will engage, where necessary, with a Database Registry (FAIRsharing in OSTrails) to retrieve information about, for example, the access, sustainability and preservation policies of the Data Repository to which the DO belongs. Finally, the individual FAIR Test results are aggregated and passed back to the user as a FAIR Result Set output (see [section 5.2.2](#)). While other solutions might exist, in OSTrails FAIRsharing will have the dual role of serving as registry describing the Metrics and Benchmarks and as a lookup service for Standards (<https://fairsharing.org/search?fairsharingRegistry=Standard>) and Databases (<https://fairsharing.org/databases>).

Figure 10. Sequence diagram of an exemplar interaction of a user with the components of the FAIR Reference Model for the purposes of executing a FAIR assessment.

There may be additional steps, requiring additional lookups in both Test and Standards registries if the user has requested the calculation of a Benchmark. For example, the instantiation in code form of a Benchmark as an Algorithm may be required to cross-reference with external data source to determine what a specific community currently considers an acceptable level of failure with respect to certain metrics, to provide its final quality assessment.

Metadata and Standards registries play a critical dual-role in the OSTrails Assessment IF (see [Deliverable 1.4](#)), which is not immediately visible in the overall OSTrails Assessment IF architecture diagrams, where the complexity of the FAIR Reference Model is hidden in favour of clarity. We anticipate that Metadata and Standards repositories will play yet another role in the context of providing guidance on how to address FAIR testing failures, as described in the next section.

4.5. Post-assessment Guidance

To date, the only in-use implementation of the (emergent) Guidance Element FTR metadata structures are: 1) the FAIR Tests written by the FAIR Champion authors (mirroring the original 22 FAIR Tests available in the FAIR Evaluator software), and 2) the prototype FAIR Champion Scoring Algorithm execution engine. In both cases, there is a link to a placeholder guidance element via the context node, together with brief human-readable text indicating what the guidance is. An example of a failed test, and the addition of a guidance element link to the output, is shown in [Figure 11](#) (“more

information” is a placeholder link to the future URL of a guidance element stored in the DANS Guidance Registry).

Benchmark Assessment Outputs

► Details

Test Results

Test ID	Result	Weight
F1-PID	indeterminate	0.0

Conclusions:

Condition	Discussion	Guidance
1	Unacceptable: Database does not mint persistent identifiers	FAIRsharing definition of persistence. More Information How to link a FAIRsharing database record to the ID schema(s) it implements. More Information

Figure 11. Screenshot of the output from FAIR Champion after execution of a Scoring Algorithm (i.e. the assessment of a Benchmark against a provided Digital Object). In the bottom right of the document are two link-outs to Guidance Elements, representing

5. Uptake of the FAIR Reference Model

5.1. Assessment Tools

5.1.1. FAIR Champion

The FAIR Champion (previously FAIR Evaluator) provides a full implementation of the portions of the FAIR Reference Model that have been decided, and a strawman implementation of the two components – Scoring Algorithm outputs and Guidance - for which the models are still under development. It queries the two registries – FAIR Assist and OSTrails Index – to populate its drop-down menus and other interfaces with any test or benchmark algorithm available in the OSTrails ecosystem. Further, Champion provides an interface that allows upload of outputs from other FTR-compliant tools, allowing them to have distinct Scoring Algorithms applied to those outputs that may not be available via the tool that natively generated them.

5.1.2. FOOPS!

The Ontology Pitfall Scanner for FAIR (FOOPS!) is a FAIR assessment tool for vocabularies and ontologies. FOOPS! has been adapted to be fully compliant with the FTR specification, including tests, metrics, algorithms and benchmarks. A catalogue of test descriptions and metrics has been made available at <https://w3id.org/foops/catalogue>, and registered in the registries supported by OSTrails (FAIRSharing, FAIR Data Point). The implementation of the Guidance Elements has been completed, but alignment with FTR is under development.

5.1.3. FAIROS

FAIROS is a FAIR assessment tool for Research Objects, defined according the RO-Crate specification.²⁶ The tool uses external tools such as F-UJI (<https://f-uji.net/>), FOOPS! [8] and RSFC (<https://github.com/oeg-upm/rsfc>) to assess datasets, ontologies and software. The FAIROS catalogue (<https://w3id.org/FAIROS/catalog>) contains the metrics and tests used by the tool to evaluate Research Objects. All tests and metrics are registered in the registries supported by OSTrails (FAIRsharing, FAIR Data Point). The implementation of guidance elements is under development.

5.1.4. FAIR Validator

The OpenAIRE Metadata Validator is designed to evaluate metadata records for research products (publications, datasets, software, and other outputs) against the OpenAIRE Guidelines, which define the minimum requirements for inclusion in the OpenAIRE Graph. The tool is being extended with FAIR evaluation capabilities, which builds on the OpenAIRE Guidelines assessment. The Validator also supports and implements the FAIR Reference Model defined by OSTrails (FTR Specification). We are currently evaluating and testing the APIs for the FTR Specification, while the models for guidance and the scoring algorithm are still under development.

5.2. Exemplar Compliant Community Benchmarks from Pilots

The creation of a FAIR benchmark by a community is dependent upon that community's knowledge of its own (meta)data structures as well as its understanding of the FAIR principles. While it can be expected that communities have deep knowledge about the data structures they use, knowledge of FAIR is generally lower. As shown in **Figure 12**, the creation of a working benchmark begins with a narrative document defining FAIR for a

²⁶ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

community and ends with the production of benchmark scores in an orchestrator such as FAIR Champion.

OSTrails Pilots have started to create their benchmarks, starting from the template ‘OSTrails FAIR Assessment - Conceptual Requirements’ document [9], and iteratively refining their definition of FAIR. The document allows pilot members to define how the FAIR principles should be implemented for that community. Working together with WP3, each pilot uses this document to create the Conceptual Components of the Assess-IF (Benchmark and associated Metrics) tailored to the needs of that community. Further iterations will result in the creation of the Software Components (Scoring Algorithms and Tests).

Figure 12. Workflow diagram of how a community (e.g. OSTrails pilots) can progress from the start of benchmark creation through to running a benchmark and providing FAIR assistance/evaluation via the benchmark score. Peach-coloured documents and components are those created by community representatives, while purple indicates contributions from the technical experts in WP3.

When creating their pilot’s narrative document using the template, representatives select an existing Metric, or create a new one for each FAIR principle relevant to their Digital Objects. Metrics can be either *generic* or *specialised*. *Generic* metrics cover domain-agnostic features, and therefore are applicable to any discipline, irrespective of the type of Digital Object being evaluated. If a principle is domain-specific, communities are suggested to create their own *specialised* metric that suits their requirements, following best practices.

While the classification of metrics as generic and specialised is useful and is intended to make it easier to create assessments, there will be circumstances where a given generic metric is a necessary part of the assessment for a community but is also insufficient to wholly describe that community's requirements for that principle. For example, a community may wish to specifically check for a particular type of DOI (e.g. one minted by a service of their choice) in addition to the presence of any GUPRI type ("any GUPRI" is the definition of the generic F1 GUID metric). In this case, the community should use two metrics, both linked to FAIR F1-GUID: the generic metric for FAIR F1-GUID, and a new specialised metric with the added requirement.

Within OSTRails, all principles have corresponding generic metrics except for I2, R1.2, R1.3, which communities must specialise for their requirements. Such specialised metrics generally need to consider the requirements of both the specific discipline and Digital Object type assessed by the benchmark.

Over 14 pilots have started their benchmarks via the template document above. Three of them have working benchmarks, explained in more detail below. These will be iteratively improved until they represent a complete definition of FAIR for the community represented by the pilot.

The next stage is to specify, implement and deploy the tests associated with any specialised metrics that have been defined. References to the tests for all metrics included in a Benchmark (generic and specialised) are gathered for use in Quality Assessment. They can be assigned weights that express their relative importance, as shown in **Figure 13**.

Test Reference	Test GUID	Pass Weight	Fail Weight	Indeterminate Weight
F1-PID	https://tests.ostrails.eu/tests/fc_unique_identifier	1	-1	0
F1-GUID	https://tests.ostrails.eu/tests/fc_unique_identifier	5	-1	0
F2	https://tests.ostrails.eu/tests/fc_structured_metadata	3	-1	0
F4	https://tests.ostrails.eu/tests/fc_searchable	1	-1	0
A1-1	https://tests.ostrails.eu/tests/fc_metadata_protocol	1	-1	0
A1-2	https://tests.ostrails.eu/tests/fc_data_authorization	1	-1	0
I1	https://tests.ostrails.eu/tests/fc_data_kr_language_weak	3	-1	0
I2	https://tests.ostrails.eu/tests/fc_metadata_uses_fair_vocabularies	5	-1	0
R1-2	https://tests.ostrails.eu/tests/fc_grounded_metadata	3	-1	0
R1-3	https://tests.ostrails.eu/tests/fc_unique_identifier	5	-1	0

Figure 13. Benchmark Quality Assessment example test specifications

Associated with the tests are Conditions, which are used to determine the pass/fail threshold for each test, or combinations of tests. Messages to display in case of success or failure of each condition are specified, along with links to Guidance documents (which are not shown in the **Figure 13** example).

Condition	Description	Formula	Success Message	Fail Message
CF1-PID	Metadata are assigned globally unique identifiers	F1-PID > 0	Acceptable: metadata are assigned globally unique identifiers	Unacceptable: metadata are not assigned globally unique identifiers
CF1-GUID	Metadata are assigned persistent identifiers	F1-GUID > 0	Acceptable: metadata are assigned persistent identifiers	Unacceptable: metadata are not assigned persistent identifiers
CF2	Data are described with rich metadata	F2 > 0	Acceptable: data are described with rich metadata	Unacceptable: data are not described with rich metadata
CF4	Metadata are registered or indexed in a searchable resource	F4 > 0	Acceptable: metadata are searchable	Unacceptable: metadata are not searchable

Figure 14. Benchmark Quality Assessment example test conditions

When a Digital Object is subjected to a Benchmark Quality Assessment, the tool used to run the assessment produces results based on the specified conditions. What format the results are in and how they are displayed to the User depends on the Assessment tool used. Figures **Figure 14** and **Figure 15** show examples of test results and conclusions as displayed by FAIR Champion.

Conclusions:		
Condition	Discussion	Guidance
1	Unacceptable: metadata are not assigned globally unique identifiers	FAIR Principles F1-GUID. More Information
2	Acceptable: metadata are assigned persistent identifiers	DANS FAIR Guidance. More Information
3	Acceptable: data are described with rich metadata	
4	Acceptable: metadata are searchable	
5	Unacceptable: the protocol is not open, free, and universally implementable	FAIR Principles A1.1. More Information DANS FAIR Guidance. More Information

Figure 15. FAIR Champion Benchmark Quality Assessment example conclusions, with guidance

5.2.1. CESSDA

The **CESSDA Data Catalogue (CDC) benchmark** is intended to ensure that the metadata records it contains are FAIR. It is of primary utility for data curators, repository managers, metadata quality assessors, and data infrastructure maintainers working with social science research data. This benchmark coordinates the FAIR assessment of CDC metadata records using a mixture of generic and specialised metrics.

APPLICABILITY

CESSDA Data Catalogue study level metadata records.

SUBJECT AREA(S) COVERED BY THIS BENCHMARK

Social science research outputs contained in the CESSDA Data Catalogue.

GUIDANCE

Documentation URLs for this benchmark and CESSDA's FAIR evaluation goals should include:

- CESSDA Vocabulary Service (<https://vocabularies.cessda.eu/>)
- CESSDA ELSST (<https://thesauri.cessda.eu/elsst-6/en/>)
- CDC DDI Profiles (<https://cmv.cessda.eu/documentation/profiles.html>)
- DANS FAIR Assessment Guidance (<https://fairassessment.dansdemo.nl/guidance>)

This benchmark currently includes ten associated metrics, with a test linked to each metric. Additional metrics and tests are under development. The available tests show a variety of possible methodologies for metric definition: use of a *generic* metric and its *generic* test, use of a *specialised* metric and its *specialised* test, and use of a *generic* metric and a *specialised* test for that metric.

- **FAIR Principle F1-PID - (Meta)data are assigned persistent identifiers** (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.e226cb>): The benchmark uses a *specialised* metric (Metadata uses CESSDA approved PIDs) and test for this principle.
- **FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Metadata persistence - Gen2-MI-A2** (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.IEZbPK>): The benchmark uses the *generic* metric and test.
- **FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Structured Metadata - Gen2-MI-F2A** (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.e05e98>): The benchmark uses the *generic* metric and test.
- **FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Metadata indexed in a searchable resource - FAIR F4** (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.e05e98>): The benchmark uses the *generic* metric and test.
- **FAIR Principles A1.1 - Open protocol for (meta)data retrieval** (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.7612c1>): The benchmark uses the *generic* metric and test.
- **FAIR Principles A1.2 - Open protocol for (meta)data retrieval** (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.8e0027>): The benchmark uses the *generic* metric and test.

- **FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Use a Knowledge Representation Language (soft) - Gen2-MI-I1A** (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.qUroF6>): The benchmark uses the *generic* metric and test.
- **FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Use a Knowledge Representation Language (soft) - Gen2-MI-I1A** The benchmark uses *specialised* sub-metrics, each having a specialised test:
 - Metadata uses CESSDA ELSST Keywords
 - Metadata uses CESSDA Topic Vocabulary
 - Metadata uses DDI Analysis Unit Vocabulary
 - Metadata uses DDI Time Method Vocabulary
 - Metadata uses DDI Mode of Collection Vocabulary
 - Metadata uses DDI Sampling Procedure Vocabulary
 - Metadata contains CESSDA Provenance Information
- **FAIR Principles R1.2: (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance** (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.3e9860>): The benchmark uses a *specialised* metric (Metadata Contains CESSDA Provenance Information) and test.
- **FAIR Principles R1.3: (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards** (<https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.87d197>): The benchmark uses a *specialised* metric (Metadata conforms to CESSDA DDI Profile) and test.

5.2.2. European Life Science Research Infrastructures (LS-RI)

The European Life Science Research Infrastructures (<https://lifescience-ri.eu/>) is a member of OSTrails Thematic Cluster 1 and has developed its benchmark using the method outlined earlier. This **FAIR Assessment of Life Science Repositories and Knowledgebases Benchmark** can be found at <https://fairsharing.org/7456>. LS-RI's current version of the template, with full information on the reasoning behind the choices of metrics and FAIR definitions, is available at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17901601>. It uses FAIRsharing to assess the FAIRness of life science repositories registered within it (i.e. repositories and knowledge bases). It is of primary utility for researchers wishing to choose an appropriate life science repository to submit their data, database managers, and the RDM community generally, including any RDM role that requires a high-level evaluation of the alignment of a repository with FAIR. This benchmark coordinates the FAIR assessment of any repository registered in FAIRsharing using metadata stored within the registry. For a repository to be assessed, it only needs to be registered in FAIRsharing.

Life science repositories are highly variable and individual datasets from disparate research areas within the discipline cannot be easily assessed using a single benchmark. Therefore, rather than using a life science dataset as input for this benchmark, the FAIRsharing URL/DOI is provided and an evaluation of the FAIR-enabling aspects at a

repository level (rather than dataset-level) will be performed. This benchmark will then provide an evaluation report for the repository as a higher-level proxy for any content within the repository. Stakeholders wishing a more granular benchmark for more specific research areas are invited to create their own benchmarks that complement this one, but which provide more tailored, dataset-specific assessments within those areas.

This benchmark currently includes four associated metrics (all of which are registered in [FAIRassist](#), powered by [FAIRsharing](#)), with a test linked to each metric. Additional metrics and tests are under development. The LS-RI benchmark showcases both the flexibility and transparency of the Assess-IF framework. Despite being under development, the available tests already show a variety of possible methodologies for metric definition: use of a *generic* metric and its *generic* test, use of a *specialised* metric and its *specialised* test, and use of a *generic* metric and a newly written *specialised* test for that metric.

- **FAIR Principle F1-GUID - (Meta)data are assigned globally unique identifiers** (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.b7f1ab>): The LS-RI benchmark re-uses the *generic* metric and test provided by OSTrails (to provide a baseline identifier check) and also creates a new *specialised* metric and test. Together, these two metrics provide a complete definition of F1-GUID for the LS-RI.
 - **FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Metadata persistence - Gen2-MI-A2** (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.IEZbPK>): LS-RI will use the *generic* metric and test to check if the identifier being passed to the benchmark is globally unique, persistent and resolvable (GUPRI), but this is insufficient for our needs and therefore will only be given a low weighting.
 - **FAIR Metric ARK F1-GUPRI - Globally unique, persistent and resolvable identifiers for database content** (<https://fairsharing.org/7455>): More importantly to our benchmark are the type(s) of identifier schemas used by the database referenced in the FAIRsharing record. Therefore, we have also created the *specialised* metric and test which uses the FAIRsharing database record metadata to check that the referenced database mints GUPRIs.
- **FAIR Principle F1-PID - (Meta)data are assigned persistent identifiers** (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.e226cb>): The LS-RI benchmark makes use of a *specialised* metric and test for this principle, instead of using the *generic* metric 'FAIR Maturity Indicator - Identifier Persistence' (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.VRo9DI>)
 - **FAIR Metric ARK F1-PID - persistent identifiers for database content** (<https://fairsharing.org/7163>): this *specialised* metric and test use the FAIRsharing database record metadata to check that the referenced database mints persistent identifiers.
- **FAIR Principles A2: metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available** (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.7c4d7f>): The LS-RI

benchmark re-uses the *generic* metric provided by OSTrails, but requires a *specialised* test to implement that metric.

- **FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Metadata persistence - Gen2-MI-A2** (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.IEZbPK>): We use the *generic* metric but our own *specialised* test; this ensures that the FAIRsharing metadata for the evaluated database record is always checked for a persistence policy using the appropriate fields within that FAIRsharing record.

5.2.3. PaNOSC - ESRF

ESRF (European Synchrotron Radiation Facility), is part of the PaNOSC (Photon and Neutron Open Science Cluster). There is a need to assess the FAIRness of the datasets generated at the ESRF facility. The **FAIR Assessment of ESRF Datasets benchmark** can be found at <https://fairsharing.org/6477>. It uses FAIRsharing metrics to assess the FAIRness of ESRF Datasets registered ESRF Data Catalogue (<https://fairsharing.org/FAIRsharing.0e42aa>).

This benchmark mainly relies on generic metrics, but also includes specialized metrics. The tests associated to the specialized metrics are under development in the [FAIR Champion](#) tool. A scoring algorithm will be associated to the benchmark and will allow dataset assessment with the [FAIR Champion](#) tool.

DOIs are created for ESRF Datasets in DataCite. Each metric (generic or specialized) ensure that the DataCite metadata is compliant with a specific requirement.

- **FAIR Principles F1-PID: (Meta)data are assigned persistent identifiers** (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.e226cb>)
 - FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Identifier Persistence - Gen2-MI-F1B (<https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.VRo9DI>)
- **FAIR Principles F1-GUID: (Meta)data are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers** (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.b7f1ab>)
 - FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Identifier Uniqueness - Gen2-MI-F1A (<https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.NHCOKK>)
- **FAIR-F2: data are described with rich metadata**
 - FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Structured Metadata - Gen2-MI-F2A (<https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.2dUpZs>)
 - FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Grounded Metadata - Gen2-MI-F2B (<https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.IXAOU2>)
- **FAIR-F3: metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes** (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.820324>)
 - FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Use of GUIDs in metadata Gen2-MI-F3 (<https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.5Xy1dl>)

- **FAIR Principles F4: (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.** (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.0c0d21>)
 - **Specialized** - FAIR Metric - The content associated to a DOI is Open Access (<https://fairsharing.org/6449>)

- **FAIR-A1.1: the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable** (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.7612c1>)
 - FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Open protocol for (meta)data retrieval Gen2-MI-A1.1 (<https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.DfMGZW>)
- **FAIR-A1.2: the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary** (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.8e0027>)
 - FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Protocol supports authentication/authorization Gen2-MI-A1.2 (<https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.VrP6sm>)
- **FAIR-A2: metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available** (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.7c4d7f>)
 - FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Metadata persistence Gen2-MI-A2 (<https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.IEZbPK>)

- **FAIR-I1: (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation** (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.ec5648>)
 - FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Use a Knowledge Representation Language (strict) Gen2-MI-I1B (<https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.l8fVBn>)
- **FAIR Principles I2: (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles** (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.96d4af>)
 - **Specialized** - FAIR Metric - DOI metadata contains a link to a community ontology term - PaNET (<https://fairsharing.org/6465>)
- **FAIR-I3: (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data** (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.ae22b8>)
 - FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Qualified outward links Gen2-MI-I3 (<https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.LLXjWx>)

- **FAIR Principles R1.1: (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license** (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.aff99f>)
 - **Specialized** - FAIR Metric - License is defined in the DOI metadata (<https://fairsharing.org/7465>)
- **FAIR Principles R1.2: (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance** (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.3e9860>)
 - **Specialized** - FAIR Metric - The dataset is cited in a publication (<https://fairsharing.org/7466>)

- **Specialized** - FAIR Metric - Author affiliation is defined in metadata (<https://fairsharing.org/7494>)
- **Specialized** - FAIR Metric - Funding information is defined in metadata (<https://fairsharing.org/7496>)

6. Conclusions and Future Work

This deliverable introduces the revised version of the FAIR Reference Model, which describes a set of Conceptual Components (i.e. tests, metrics, benchmarks and scoring algorithms) to achieve transparent and interoperable FAIR assessment. The deliverable emphasizes the main additions made to the Reference Model in the FTR specification, i.e. the Scoring Algorithms and Guidance Elements, which aim to go beyond reporting whether a test is successful or not by suggesting users which steps to follow to increase the FAIRness of their Digital Objects.

The deliverable also reports on the key role of metadata registries in FAIR assessment, how different FAIR assessment tool developers have successfully adopted the FTR specification, and how different communities have begun to configure which metrics are appropriate for their benchmarks.

In the remainder of the project, OSTrails participants will focus on several lines of work: 1) Improving the FAIR Guidance Vocabulary ontology to be more mature and robust. 2) Investigating the inclusion of maturity levels, so the guidance registry may support a sort of graded compliance assistance. 3) Improving adoption of the guidance elements and scoring algorithms by FAIR assessment tools. 4) Polishing and increasing the adoption of community benchmarks by the OSTrails pilots.

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